

METHODS FOR DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF STAFF TURNOVER IN AN ORGANIZATION

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the issues and methods of improving the personnel management system. For the full and continuous development of any organization, the level of staff turnover is one of the main factors in the development of the organization. Determining the level of staff turnover enables the manager to plan activities competently. Rational regulation of staff turnover makes it possible to form an effective personnel structure of the organization. The article has developed a software module for analyzing staff turnover on the example of enterprises engaged in the production of polyethylene products.

Keywords: personnel accounting, monitoring, staff turnover, composition and structure of the causes of staff turnover, statistical reporting, satisfaction with the organization of labor and production.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена вопросам и методам совершенствования системы управления персоналом. Для полноценного и непрерывного развития любой организации уровень текучести персонала является одним из основных факторов развития организации. Определение уровня текучести персонала даёт возможность руководителю грамотно планировать деятельность. Рациональное регулирование текучести персонала позволяет формировать эффективный кадровый состав организации. В статье разработан программный модуль для анализа текучести кадров на примере предприятия занимающийся производством полиэтиленовых изделий.

Ключевые слова: учет персонала, мониторинг, текучесть кадров, состав и структура причины текучести кадров, статистическая отчетности, удовлетворенность организацией труда и производства.

Annotatsiya: Maqola xodimlarni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish masalalari va usullariga bag'ishlangan. Har qanday tashkilotning to'liq va uzluksiz rivojlanishi uchun xodimlarning aylanmasi darajasi tashkilotning rivojlanishining asosiy omillaridan biridir. Xodimlarning aylanmasi darajasini aniqlash menejerga faoliyatni to'g'ri rejalashtirish imkonini beradi. Xodimlar aylanmasini oqilona tartibga solish tashkilotning samarali kadrlar tarkibini shakllantirishga imkon beradi. Maqolada polietilen mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish bilan shug'ullanadigan korxonada kadrlar aylanmasini tahlil qilish uchun dasturiy modul ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: xodimlarni hisobga olish, xodimlarni monitoring qilish, xodimlar aylanmasi, xodimlar aylanmasi sabablari tarkibi va tuzilmasi, statistik hisobot, mehnat va ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etishdan qoniqish.

I. Introduction

The personnel of the organization is the most difficult object of management. Unlike tangible assets, people are able to make decisions independently and assess the requirements imposed on them. In addition, the staff is a team, each member of which has its own interests and is very sensitive to managerial influences, and the reaction to them is often difficult to predict.[1] Staff turnover or staff turnover is an indicator of how many employees are leaving the company. After all, after the departure of employees, it is necessary to find new ones who will meet all the

requirements and will be able to quickly adapt to a new place.[2]

The personnel management system is a set of software solutions used to optimize and automate the management of human resources and related processes throughout the employee's life cycle. Since the HR department is not usually seen as the core of profit, the business case should be focused on reducing administrative and technological costs, increasing efficiency and improving knowledge through analytics while supporting the organization's core business needs[3]. The analysis of data on employees who

have left the organization provides information on the basis of which, it can be assumed, the direction of further research to establish the causes and determine the means to overcome staff turnover. In the process of collecting and analyzing staff turnover indicators, it is important to obtain information on various categories of employees, especially those who are difficult to find and retain, for example, highly skilled workers and knowledge workers [4]. The analysis of human resource losses requires detailed information about the work experience of retiring employees in order to identify problem areas and develop options for overcoming them.

II. MAIN PART

The authors [5] identified several indicators and methods for measuring the movement and turnover of personnel. Below are the steps for managing staff turnover:

1. Setting the degree of staff turnover. In this case, a quantitative indicator is determined and its value and deviation from the average are established. It is considered to be a normative level of 5-7%. But it should not be perceived as a kind of indicator, since the movement of personnel at a particular enterprise is carried out under the influence of a combination of factors: industry affiliation, production technology, labor intensity of work, the presence or absence of a seasonality factor in the production cycle, management style, level and principles of corporate culture. Therefore, when determining the level of staff turnover, it is necessary to analyze the dynamics of the company's labor indicators for as long as possible, to identify the presence and magnitude of seasonal fluctuations in turnover.

2. Setting the amount of economic losses that staff turnover will lead to. This is one of the most important stages. Additional calculations are required for its implementation. This data consists of an analysis of the damage and additional costs associated with the following factors:

- loss of time at work;
- costs of training and retraining of new employees;
- drop in the output of employees before dismissal;
- low level of output of newly hired employees;
- the costs of recruiting staff who quit for reasons related to staff turnover.

3. Finding out the reasons for the dismissal of employees in general and, in particular, for reasons of staff turnover. Staff turnover may be caused by

an industry-specific feature of an enterprise's activity or an imperfection of its management system. Then it is necessary to determine the structure of the motives of staff turnover. It is based on the real reasons that make an employee want to make a decision to leave the organization[6].

4. Definition of a system of measures aimed at stabilizing the team. To do this, three groups of measures are being taken to reduce staff turnover:

- this is the improvement of working conditions, improvement of the system of material incentives, organization and management of production, etc., related to technical and economic measures;
- improvement of labor adaptation technologies, professional promotion systems, etc., related to organizational measures;
- improvement of leadership styles and methods and relationships in the team, the system of moral encouragement, etc. related to socio-psychological measures.

5. Calculation of performance indicators from the implementation of the developed measures (monitoring). After that, a comparative analysis of the costs of carrying out measures to optimize staff turnover and loss due to a high level of turnover is carried out. If the costs of solving the problem exceed the losses caused by high staff turnover, then it is necessary to find new, other, optimal options for working with personnel.

There are several methods for assessing staff turnover: staff turnover index, survival rate, stability index.

Employee turnover indicator. The staff turnover indicator determines the amount of the organization's losses and is calculated according to the formula (1). Due to its simplicity, this indicator has several disadvantages, the main one of which is that it covers the entire organization as a whole, without considering individual groups of employees in which this indicator may differ greatly [7].

$$ED(t) = \frac{U(t)}{R(t)}, \quad (1)$$

where t is the time period under consideration, $U(t)$ is the number of people who left for a certain period, $R(t)$ is the average number of employees working for a certain period.

The survival indicator shows the proportion of employees remaining at the enterprise after a certain period of time. It is calculated according to the formula (2). Such an indicator can determine

the number of employees that need to be accepted today, so that after a certain time a certain number of highly qualified employees will turn out.

$$S = P(t_2) - P(t_1), \quad (2)$$

where p_1 – start date of the period, p_2 – end of the period, $E(p)$ – number of employees working on the date t .

The stability indicator shows the number of employees with long work experience who seek to stay working, and therefore shows the degree of continuity of employment in the enterprise. Calculated by the formula (3) [8].

$$I = \frac{E}{EC}, \quad (3)$$

где E – number of employees with more than a year of experience, EC – number of employees who got a job a year ago.

Let's consider the calculation of the staff turnover coefficient at the enterprise for the manufacture of polyethylene products. The total number of employees of the company is 1760 people, 98 employees quit during the year. Of them: at their own request – 81 people; at the initiative of the manager– 2 people; due to retirement – 7 people; due to illness – 8 people. The calculation of the coefficient includes only employees who quit at their own request and on the initiative of the management. This calculation can be performed using a common formula that serves as an indicator for evaluation and analysis:

$$W_k = \frac{R_o + R_l}{N_e} * 100 \quad (4)$$

Where, W_k - the desired coefficient, R_o – the number of employees who quit at their own request, R_l – the number of people who quit at the initiative of the management, N_e - number of employees in total.

Calculate the staff turnover:

$$W_k = \frac{81+2}{1760} * 100 \quad (5)$$

The result obtained is 4.71%. It can be concluded that the result meets the requirements of the norms. In the course of solving the problems of the personnel turnover calculation system, it was decided to create an online service in the programming language JavaScript. The system interface is shown in figure 1, users need to fill in the fields, choose branch and click on the calculation button, then we can see the result as a percentage. To calculate turnover rate, we divide the number of terminates during a specific period by the number of employees at the beginning of that period.

Fig 1. Interface of ET calculator

After entering the data, we will get the result in the form:

Fig 2. Result of calculation after input data

At the next stage, it is important to determine the losses that the organization has suffered due to staff turnover. This is a rather complex and time-consuming process, which includes the analysis of some processes. Next, it is necessary to find out the reasons for staff turnover. At the last stage, it is necessary to develop systems of measures to reduce excessive turnover and improve the procedure for hiring and firing employees.

III. CONCLUSION

For dynamically developing large organizations actively implementing modern information technologies in order to increase overall economic efficiency, mechanisms for building rational organizational structures, taking into account the redistribution of staff duties, the results of the analysis of the need for their training and competence assessment, are of great practical interest[9]. Monitoring turnover is an important function of human resources management. Companies want to monitor the movement of employees out of the organization so they can look for and minimize causes of turnover. Controlling turnover is one of the many quantitative ways the HR department can affect the bottom line. It can be concluded that a naturally high level of staff

turnover in many cases indicates the presence of major gaps in personnel management and enterprise management as a whole, this is a kind of coefficient of disadvantage. Analysis and research of the literature on the problems of fluidity, allowed us to conclude that, despite the requests of practice, science has not yet developed a holistic concept and technology for managing this process. However, the consequences of turnover depend both on its quantitative size and on the qualitative composition of the dismissed (dismissed) employees of the enterprise in question. Therefore, the basis of the concept of reducing staff turnover should be both ensuring an increase in the efficiency of the organization as a whole, and the widespread development of its human resources potential in comparison with changes in the

external environment, as well as programs for the adaptation of accepted personnel. When regulating staff turnover, it is necessary to maintain certain proportions within various categories of personnel, striving to form a rational personnel structure of the organization. Society is able to turn the challenges caused by changes in the global labor market into opportunities that will strengthen the development of society. This requires appropriate government policies, national and global strategies aimed at increasing the number of jobs, ensuring decent wages, protecting the safety and rights of workers, ensuring equal opportunities for all, common prosperity and accelerated human development[10-11].

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